

1 Statistical Analysis Plan

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63 2 Abbreviations and Definitions

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Abbreviation	Definition
<i>HAI</i>	<i>Healthcare-associated infection</i>
<i>ICC</i>	<i>Intraclass correlation coefficient</i>
<i>IPC</i>	<i>Infection prevention and control</i>
<i>NOIS</i>	<i>Norwegian Surveillance System for Antibiotic Use and Healthcare-Associated Infections</i>
<i>NOST</i>	<i>National Tool for Observation of Infection Prevention Measures</i>
<i>NPR</i>	<i>Norwegian Patient Registry</i>
<i>POSI</i>	<i>Postoperative site infection</i>
<i>RD</i>	<i>Risk difference</i>
<i>RR</i>	<i>Risk ratio</i>
<i>VESUV</i>	<i>Norwegian Institute of Public Health's web-based outbreak notification system</i>

65 3 Introduction

66 3.1 Preface

67 Effective infection prevention and control (IPC) is essential to ensure high-quality healthcare services.
 68 Infections that occur during hospitalization and because of services provided may interfere with the
 69 outcome of needed medical treatments. To prevent healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), it is
 70 essential that all healthcare personnel are well trained in and follow standard IPC measures during
 71 patient care. Standard precautions include hand hygiene, use of personal protective equipment and
 72 more.

73

74 The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) is introducing a new electronic tool and national
 75 template for direct observation of compliance with recommended IPC measures in healthcare. The
 76 solution is called the National Tool for Observation of Infection Prevention Measures (NOST). NOST is
 77 a quality improvement tool that includes a web-based solution for observing and recording the degree
 78 of compliance with recommendations for hand hygiene and other IPC measures.

79

80 The trial protocol is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/7648821>

81 3.2 Research Questions

82 Would risk of compliance with hand hygiene recommendations by employees who perform patient-
 83 related work in Norwegian hospital wards (*population*), measured at one-year postimplementation
 84 (*primary outcome*), be different if wards were to implement and adhere to NOST (*intervention*)
 85 compared to if NOST was not implemented and not adhered to (*control*)?

86

87 Would risk of outbreaks and infections among inpatients at Norwegian hospitals, measured over one-
 88 year postimplementation (*example secondary outcomes*), be different if wards were to implement
 89 and adhere to NOST (*intervention*) compared to if NOST was not implemented and not adhered to
 90 (*control*)?

91

92 These questions are about the effect of implementing and adhering to NOST, not the effect of a policy
 93 that a ward should implement NOST. This has important implications for the estimands and
 94 estimators.

95

96 **4 Study Methods**

97 **4.1 General Study Design and Plan**

98

Populations	1. Employees in Norwegian hospitals who perform patient-related work. 2. Inpatients in Norwegian hospitals. 3. Norwegian hospital wards.
Intervention	<u>Implementing NOST</u>
Control	<u>Not implementing NOST</u>
Primary outcome	Compliance with hand hygiene recommendations by hospital employees who do patient-related work, measured at one year after randomization.
Design	Cluster-randomized parallel two-arm superiority trial.
Blinding	Trial participants and other personnel cannot be blinded to treatment allocation. The trial statistician will be blinded to treatment allocation.
Treatment allocation	Hospital wards will be randomized 1:1. Randomization will be stratified by hospital to ensure approximately equal allocation of wards within hospital.

99

The following diagram illustrates the sequence and duration of the study periods:

100
101

102
103

The following table shows the structure of data registered in NOST:

104
105

Place			Observation of hand hygiene			Person
Hospital	Ward	Section number	Observation number	Indication	Compliance	Profession
1	5	1	1	A	1	Nurse
			2	B	1	
			3	D	0	
1	4	2	4	B	1	Physician
2	2	3	5	A	0	Nurse
			6	B	1	
			7	C	0	
			8	C	0	

			9	E	1	
1	5	4	10	A	1	Nurse
			11	E	1	assistant

106

107

Description of the variables:

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4.2 General Study Populations and Inclusion-Exclusion Criteria

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135

There are three general study populations (see above and the study protocol). This SAP introduces a third population not specified in the protocol, hospital ward. This was introduced because one of the secondary outcomes (outbreaks) cannot be measured at the level of employee or inpatient but can be measured at the level of ward.

We will exclude hospitals and their associated randomized wards from all analyses if the hospital after randomization decides not to implement or to terminate the execution of NOST, and the decision is communicated to the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

136

4.3 Treatment Allocation

137

138

139

140

Stratified randomization will be used to allocate wards to 1:1 intervention and control arms. Randomization will be stratified by hospital. Randomization will be performed using a computer-based system and the investigators will not be able to manipulate treatment allocation. The approach is outlined in the protocol.

141

4.4 Blinding/Masking

142

143

144

145

146

It is not possible to blind trial participants or observers to treatment allocation. While much of the outcome data will be obtained from registries (e.g., to which events are notified), the people who report data may not be blinded to treatment allocation. However, the trial statistician who will analyze the data will be blinded to treatment allocation.

147 When all data have been collected, a member of the research group will apply a blind to the treatment
 148 allocation variable, so that the statistician will not know which arms correspond to the intervention
 149 and control treatments. The analysis of the primary outcome will be performed blinded. Before
 150 unblinding, we will publish a short document on Zenodo describing how the result for the primary
 151 outcome was interpreted by the project team. The blind will then be removed and the secondary
 152 analyses will be performed unblinded.

153 5 Outcomes

154 5.1 Primary outcome

155 The primary outcome is compliance with hand hygiene recommendations by hospital employees who
 156 do patient-related work. Compliance will be assessed one year after randomization by trained and
 157 experienced observers. The observers will record the number of observations made and the number
 158 of these observations that meet the criteria for compliance. The number of observations and
 159 compliances will be measured at the level of hospital ward. Compliance will therefore be aggregated
 160 at the level of hospital ward and the primary outcome is a count variable.

161 5.2 Secondary outcomes

162 As for the primary outcome, all secondary outcomes will be aggregated at the level of hospital ward.
 163 Unlike the primary outcome, all secondary outcomes are measured over the one-year trial period
 164 (from study start) rather than at the end of the trial. For data from VESUV, all wards are included. For
 165 NOIS data, only wards participating in the surveillance are included. For data from NPR, only inpatient
 166 wards are included, excluding emergency departments and short-stay units that are not registered in
 167 NPR.
 168

Secondary Outcome	Type	Denominator	Data source
<i>Infectious disease outbreaks</i>			
1. Outbreak	Count	Wards	VESUV
2. Inpatient infection	Count	Inpatients in wards with outbreaks	
3. Employee infection	Count	Employees in wards with outbreaks	
<i>Surveillance of HAI</i>			
4. Inpatient infection	Count	Inpatients included in the surveillance	NOIS
5. Inpatient antibiotic treatment	Count	Inpatients included in the surveillance	
<i>Surveillance of postoperative site infections</i>			
6. Inpatient treatment for postoperative site infection	Count	Surgical inpatients included in the surveillance	NOIS-POSI
<i>Infectious disease diagnoses</i>			
7. Inpatient HAI diagnosis in total and by type of infection	Count	Admitted patients in ward-based care	NPR
8. Infectious disease diagnosis			

169

170

171 **6 Sample Size**

172 Assuming $\alpha = 0.05$, $\beta = 0.8$, a control risk of 0.4, an intervention risk of 0.6 (i.e., the treatment effect
173 is a risk difference of at least 0.2), an ICC of 0.1, an average cluster size of 30 observations among
174 hospital employees who do patient-related work, a loss of 2 d.f. for adjustment of cluster-level
175 covariates, and stratification by hospital, it was estimated that at least 52 hospital wards should be
176 recruited (26 in each arm).

177 **7 General Analysis Considerations**

178 **7.1 Timing of Analyses**

179 Analyses will be performed after the database is locked. No interim or follow-up analyses are planned.

180 **7.2 Analysis Sets**

181 Although this SAP defines three populations, when analyzing primary and secondary outcome, there
182 is only a single analysis set that will contain all wards randomized and not excluded (see exclusion
183 criteria, above). In practical terms, the data set will have one ward per row and there will be 9 outcome
184 variables (columns), plus covariates. Outcomes will be analyzed in the arms to which the wards were
185 randomized.

186 **7.3 Covariates and Subgroups**

187 Because randomization is stratified by hospital, we originally planned to adjust for hospital as a fixed
188 effect in all analyses. However, the planned adjustment would require estimating one parameter for
189 each hospital (minus the reference hospital), in addition to treatment effect. The large number of
190 parameters that would therefore need to be estimated could lead to imprecision on the effect
191 estimates and possibly also estimation problems. Further, the trial is unlikely to include all hospitals
192 in Norway and hence the sample will not exhaust all possible levels of the hospital variable. For these
193 reasons, and the chosen regression model (see section 9), we will account for the likely clustering of
194 outcomes within hospital using cluster-robust standard errors, with hospital as the cluster variable.

195
196 We will obtain data on the following variables to support four subgroup analyses:

- 197
198 1. Hospital department (e.g., psychiatry, orthopedics, neurology, ...)
199 2. Employee profession (e.g., physician, nurse, ...)
200 3. Indications of hand hygiene (e.g., before patient contact, after exposure to body fluid,)

201
202 These subgroups are based on the hypothesis that baseline hand hygiene compliance may differ by
203 type of ward or type of profession with different levels of education or work tasks, and compliance
204 may vary depending on the situations in which hand hygiene is recommended. It may be the case that
205 treatment effect is different in these subgroups. (For example, if some ward types already have
206 exceptionally high baseline compliance with hand hygiene recommendations, then only a small
207 beneficial treatment effect is possible for this subgroup. Conversely, if a type of ward or profession
208 has exceptionally low baseline compliance for all or some of the indications then a large beneficial
209 treatment effect may be achievable in this subgroup.

210
211 Ward type is based on the designation of each ward in the trial. If over 5% of wards do not provide
212 primary outcome data, missing data will be handled as outlined in section 7.5. Type of profession and
213 hand hygiene indication are documented during each observation, and the dataset is not expected to
214 have missing data for these subgroups. As a result, only recorded (complete) cases are included in

215 analyses pertaining to these subgroups.
216

217 **7.4 Multiple Centers**

218 We will not combine outcomes by ward or hospital (i.e., we will not define “pseudo-centers”). We will
219 not explore treatment-by-hospital interactions. Between-hospital differences in risk of compliance,
220 for example, will be accounted for using cluster-robust standard errors with hospital as the cluster
221 variable.

222 **7.5 Missing Data**

223 We will examine the data for spurious values and seek to verify or obtain correct values if data are
224 miscoded (e.g., negative counts, nonintegral values entered for counts, or counts that appear to be
225 unrealistically large). We will report any data processing decisions that need to be made at the time
226 of analysis.

227
228 It is very unlikely that data will be missing for the treatment, hospital, or ward variables, which are
229 needed in all analyses.

230
231 Data may be missing for the primary outcome variable, which is measured by observers. It is unlikely
232 that data will be missing for the secondary outcome variables, which will be obtained from registries,
233 but data will be missing if hospitals do not provide data to the registries (Norwegian Institute of Public
234 Health).

235
236 If wards do not provide outcome data for the primary outcome, we will contact them and ask them to
237 provide the missing data. If more than 5% of wards do not provide primary outcome data, we will use
238 Little’s test to assess if the data are unlikely to be missing completely at random (MCAR) but missing
239 at random (MAR). If we assess the data to be MAR, we will use multiple imputation by chained
240 equations (MICE) and perform the prespecified analyses including all wards.

241
242 The primary outcome comprises counts of observations and counts of those observations that meet
243 the criteria for compliance. We anticipate that both counts will be missing for wards that do not
244 provide outcome data. It will therefore be necessary to impute missing values for these variables in a
245 way that ensures both are valid counts, and that the number of compliances is not greater than the
246 number of observations imputed for a given ward. We will do this as follows.

247
248 For each ward with non-missing primary outcome data, we will compute a point estimate of the
249 logit risk of compliance as $w_i = \text{logit } r_i = \log r_i - \log(1 - r_i)$, where $r_i = n_i/N_i$. Within the MICE
250 framework, we will impute logit risks for wards with missing primary outcome data (e.g., using a linear
251 model with normal errors), and hence risks for wards with missing primary outcome data as
252 $r_i = 1/(1 + e^{-w_i})$, where w_i is an imputed logit risk. Missing observation counts (N_i) will be modelled
253 using a Poisson model. This may impute that no observations were made in some wards. We will
254 address this issue by replacing zero observation counts with ones. Finally, we will impute the number
255 of compliances for the wards with missing primary outcome data as the passive variable $\lfloor N_i r_i + 1/2 \rfloor$
256 (i.e., “rounding half up” a possibly non-integral number of imputed compliances to an integer), where
257 N_i and r_i are imputed as described above. The r_i will not be used in subsequent analyses.

258
259 The imputation model for the primary outcome will include:

- 260
261
- Treatment assignment

- 262 • Adherence (if available; see section 7.6)
- 263 • Hospital (assuming data are not missing for all wards in a hospital)
- 264 • Hospital region
- 265 • Type of department
- 266 • The secondary outcomes (on the basis that the primary outcome is likely to be highly correlated
- 267 with other outcomes)

268

269 If we cannot assess that the data are likely MAR and cannot rule out the possibility that the data are
270 missing not at random (MNAR), we will perform complete case analyses, but will not draw strong
271 conclusions about the causal effect of NOST and report the missing data as a possible limitation.

272

273 The secondary outcomes depend on registry data. It is possible that some wards or hospitals will either
274 never report data or will intermittently report data. Both possibilities represent missing outcome data
275 problems. We will therefore follow the same general approach as for missing primary outcome data.
276 In the case that secondary outcome data is known to be intermittently reported (i.e., data for some
277 collection periods are available for certain wards, but no data have been reported by the wards for
278 other periods), we will use MICE to impute for the collection periods with missing data and then
279 compute the total number of inpatients infected (for example). The imputed outcome is therefore a
280 function of imputed variables (a “passive” variable), which should be handled carefully in the analysis.
281 In Stata, it is necessary to use the syntax “**mi passive: generate...**” or
282 “**mi register passive...**”, prior to “**mi estimate:...**” to ensure the passive variables are
283 generated correctly in the imputed data sets. In R, passive variables can be handled using the approach
284 described in section 3.4 of van Buuren and Groothuis-Oudshoorn [1].

285

286 Unless legally or ethically prohibited, we will report any missing data and wards or hospitals that
287 cannot be included in analysis, for example due to withdrawal from the trial.

288 7.6 Intercurrent Events

289 Recall from section 3.2 that the research question is about the effect of implementing and adhering
290 to NOST. We anticipate that some wards may not adhere or fully adhere to the treatment to which
291 they were randomized. For example, a ward may have been randomized to implement and adhere to
292 NOST for the one-year period of the trial, but either did not implement NOST or did not fully adhere.
293 Similarly, a ward may have been randomized to the control arm (i.e., to not implement NOST), but
294 NOST was partially or fully implemented. Because such events would occur after randomization and
295 would change the interpretation of the outcome from that originally intended and hence give a
296 treatment effect estimate that does not have the intended interpretation, non-adherence can be
297 treated as an intercurrent event (ICE) [2].

298

299 All estimands (see section 9) for which statistical analyses will be performed utilize collapsible
300 measures of effect (risk ratio or mean difference). This allows any non-adherence to be addressed via
301 regression adjustment. We will measure adherence using the proportion of time after randomization
302 up to one year after study start (i.e., adherence will be measured using a value between 0 and 1,
303 inclusive).

304

305 If 5% or more wards do not fully adhere to their randomized treatment, we will estimate the effect of
306 being randomized and adhering to NOST as the sum (on the log scale for ratio effect measures) of two
307 effects: randomization to NOST and adherence to NOST. Note that adherence to NOST will also be
308 measured in the control arm to facilitate the estimation of the effect of full versus no adherence to
309 NOST. We will then exponentiate the sum to obtain the desired estimate of treatment effect.

310

311 If fewer than 5% of wards do not adhere to their randomized treatment we will not account for the
 312 non-adherence, but report it is a possible limitation.

313 8 Summary of Study Data

314 A CONSORT trial flow diagram will be presented.

315

316 A table of baseline characteristics will be presented following CONSORT guidelines, as follows.
 317 Continuous variables will be summarized using the following descriptive statistics: median and
 318 interquartile range (IQR). The frequencies and percentages of observed levels will be reported for
 319 categorical variables. Baseline characteristics will be reported in a table like the following:

320

		Control (N = XXX)	NOST (N = XXX)
Hospitals	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Number of beds	Median [IQR]	XXX [XXX to XXX]	XXX [XXX to XXX]
Health region			
North	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Central	N (%)	XXX	XXX
...
South-East	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Wards	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Health region			
North	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Central	N (%)	XXX	XXX
...
South-East	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Department			
Oncology	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Orthopedics	N (%)	XXX	XXX
...
Neurology	N (%)	XXX	XXX
Profession			
Physician	N (%)	XXX	XXX
...
Nurse	N (%)	XXX	XXX

321

322

323

324 Effect estimates for the primary and secondary outcomes will be reported in a table like the following:

325

	Control	Intervention	Risk Ratio (95% CI)	p-value	Risk Difference (95% CI)
Primary outcome					
Compliance	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
Secondary outcomes					
Outbreaks	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
Patients infected	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
...

326

327 Effect estimates for the subgroup analyses for the primary outcome will be reported in a table like the
 328 following:
 329

	Control	Intervention	Risk Ratio (95% CI)	p-value	Risk Difference (95% CI)
Department					
Psychiatry	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
Orthopedics	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
...
Neurology	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
Profession					
Physician	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
...
Nurse	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
Indication					
Before patient contact	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]
...
After exposure to body fluid	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX/XXX (XXX%)	XXX [XXX to XXX]	0.XXX	XXX [XXX to XXX]

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 331
 332
 333
 334
 335

336 **8.1 Derived Variables**

337 The secondary outcomes are derived from ongoing notifications or from reports that hospitals should
 338 submit for specific periods, e.g. four times a year. For example, the number of HAIs (NOIS) over the
 339 one-year trial period would be the sum of such reports. This has implications for imputation, if some
 340 hospitals do not report data for one or more of the four-month periods (see section 7.5).

341 **8.2 Protocol Deviations**

342 Any deviations from the original protocol or this SAP will be reported and justified.

343 **9 Estimation and Analyses**

344 While this trial is cluster-randomized (ward is the cluster), outcome data will be measured at the level
 345 of ward. The unit of randomization and the unit of analysis are therefore identical. It is not necessary
 346 to account for cluster randomization as in trials where clusters of units are randomized, and outcomes
 347 are measured on the units.
 348

349 **9.1 Risk Ratio Estimation**

350 If fewer than 5% of wards do not adhere to their randomized treatment, we will estimate marginal
 351 risk ratios (RRs) using binomial regression without accounting for the non-adherence. For the primary
 352 and most of the secondary outcomes, this is:

353

354
$$n_i \sim B(N_i, p_i) \text{ where } \log p_i = \beta_0 + \beta_x x_i$$

355

356 With respect to the primary outcome, n_i is the number of compliances in the i th hospital ward, N_i is

357 the number of observations made in the i th hospital ward, β_0 estimates log risk in control, x_i indicates
 358 if the i th hospital ward was randomized to NOST, β_X estimates the effect of being randomized to NOST
 359 as a marginal log risk ratio. The marginal log risk ratio of being randomized to and adhering to NOST
 360 is estimated by β_X .

361

362 If 5% or more wards do fully not adhere to their randomized treatment, we will estimate marginal risk
 363 ratios (RRs) using binomial regression as follows:

364

$$n_i \sim B(N_i, p_i) \text{ where } \log p_i = \beta_0 + \beta_X x_i + \beta_A a_i$$

365

366 Here, $0 \leq a_i \leq 1$ models the degree of adherence by the i th hospital ward to NOST (see section 7.6)
 367 with $a_i = 0$ corresponding to non-adherence and $a_i = 1$ corresponding to full adherence, and β_A
 368 estimates the effect of full adherence to NOST. The marginal log risk ratio of being randomized to and
 369 adhering to NOST is estimated by $\beta_X + \beta_A$. Note that the x_i and a_i may be highly correlated (almost
 370 collinear) because we expect that most wards that implement NOST will also adhere to NOST. For this
 371 reason, we will not interpret β_X and β_A separately. We will assume that the statistical software will
 372 cope well with the high correlation but will address this issue during analysis in the case of
 373 nonconvergence.

374

375 Estimation can be performed using Stata as follows (see footnote 1 on page 14):

376

```
377 binreg compliances i.treat c.adh, n(observations) rr vce(cluster hospital)
```

378

379 where data are arranged with one ward per row, **compliances** is a variable containing the numbers
 380 of observations where the employees comply, **treat** is a treatment indicator where 1 indicates
 381 randomization to NOST, **adh** is a variable containing adherences (which would be omitted if fewer
 382 than 5% of wards do not adhere to their randomized treatment), **observations** is a variable
 383 containing the numbers of observations made, and **hospital** is a factor variable that codes for the
 384 hospital to which the wards belong. Treatment effect can then be estimated on the log scale using:

385

```
386 lincom _b[1.treat] + _b[adh]
```

387

388 Estimation can be performed using R as follows:

389

```
390 model <- glm(cbind(compliance_success, compliance_failure) ~ treat + adh,  

  391           data = df,  

  392           family = binomial(link = "log")  

  393 coeftest(df, vcov. = vcovCL(model, cluster = hospital)  

  394 lincom <- glht(model, linfct = c(treat + adh = 0)
```

395

396 If the analysis is performed in R after imputation (see section 7.5), the script will be run in a loop
 397 through all imputed data sets before estimates and standard errors are combined using the pool()
 398 function in the "mice" package.

399

400 The variable names may differ in the actual data set.

401

402 For each risk ratio estimate, we will also compute an indicative risk difference (RD; see the tables in
 403 section 8). This will be done by taking the difference between a point estimate of the control risk and
 404 the product of that control risk and the estimated risk ratio. The indicative RD will be presented by
 405 with a 95% confidence interval.

406

407

408 We will calculate and report intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC). To be able to perform an ICC
 409 computation, the data will be analyzed using a binomial generalized linear mixed model (glmer) on a
 410 logit scale, instead of using the log binomial model described above. The results will be converted
 411 from the logit to the risk ratio scale using the delta method to transform the standard errors, and then
 412 the ICCs will be computed. The reported ICCs will therefore be correlations on the logit scale.

413 9.1.1 Sensitivity analyses of adherence definition

414 The estimator proposed for the case that 5% or more wards do fully not adhere to their randomized
 415 treatment involves accounting for an intercurrent event (incomplete adherence to NOST due to, for
 416 example, late start or cessation) by estimating the log risk ratio of being randomized to and adhering
 417 to NOST as $\beta_X + \beta_A$, where a_i , the variable for coefficient β_A , is a continuous variable in $[0, 1]$ with
 418 $a_i = 0$ modelling no adherence to NOST and $a_i = 1$ modelling full adherence to NOST. Because this
 419 analysis requires a modelling assumption, we will perform sensitivity analyses for each analysis that
 420 uses the model proposed.

421
 422 In the first sensitivity analysis, we will estimate marginal risk ratios using a restricted estimation
 423 sample that will exclude wards that did not adhere to the treatment to which they were assigned (i.e.,
 424 we will exclude wards randomized to NOST which did not fully implement NOST, and exclude wards
 425 randomized to control that partially or fully implemented NOST). The restricted estimation sample will
 426 be analyzed using the following model:

$$427$$

$$428 n_i \sim B(N_i, p_i) \text{ where } \log p_i = \beta_0 + \beta_X x_i$$

$$429$$

430 where the log risk ratio of fully adhering to NOST is estimated by β_X .

431
 432 In the second sensitivity analysis, we will model adherence using a factor variable, with $k + 1$ levels
 433 that model degree of adherence to NOST. We will estimate marginal risk ratios (RRs) using binomial
 434 regression as follows:

$$435$$

$$436 n_i \sim B(N_i, p_i) \text{ where } \log p_i = \beta_0 + \beta_X x_i + \beta_{A1} a_{i1} + \beta_{A2} a_{i2} + \dots + \beta_{Ak} a_{ik}$$

$$437$$

438 where $\{a_{i1}, a_{i2}, \dots, a_{ik}\}$ are binary variables that indicate the non-reference levels of the factor
 439 variable that models adherence (these variables will be created automatically in software), and
 440 $\{\beta_{A1}, \beta_{A2}, \dots, \beta_{Ak}\}$ are log risk ratios for the non-reference levels. We will define the reference
 441 (i.e., base) level to be no adherence to NOST and estimate the effect of being randomized and
 442 adhering to NOST as $\beta_X + \beta_{A1}$, where β_{A1} is the log risk ratio for the level of the factor variable
 443 corresponding to full adherence to NOST.

444
 445 Having obtained the three estimates of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST (i.e., one
 446 from the analysis specified in section 9.1 and one for each of the two sensitivity analyses), we will
 447 assess the sensitivity of our estimates to the assumptions underpinning the three models using
 448 seemingly unrelated estimation¹ (SUE) as follows. Let $\{\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3\}$ denote the three estimates on the
 449 log risk ratio scale. Sensitivity will be assessed using a two-sided Wald test of the hypothesis
 450 $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \gamma_3$. We will report the result of this test and interpret the p-value according to the following
 451 table:

452

¹ Note that, in Stata, use of SUE requires that clustering within hospital be specified as an option to **suest** rather than **binreg** for all models, and that the variance-covariance matrix of the estimates (VCE) be computed using the observed, rather than the expected, information matrix (i.e., using the **vce(oim)** option of **binreg**).

P-value	Estimates γ_1 , γ_2 , and γ_3 all statistically exclude no effect	Interpretation
<0.05	Yes, same directions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The magnitude of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST <u>is sensitive</u> to modelling assumptions. The direction of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST <u>is not sensitive</u> to modelling assumptions.
<0.05	Yes, different directions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One or both sensitivity analyses disagreed with the main estimator of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST. The effect of the intervention is unclear.
<0.05	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One or both sensitivity analyses disagreed with the main estimator of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST. The effect of the intervention is unclear.
≥ 0.05	Yes, same directions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The magnitude of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST <u>is not sensitive</u> to modelling assumptions. The direction of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST <u>is not sensitive</u> to modelling assumptions.
≥ 0.05	Yes, different directions	<i>This condition is nonsensical: it should not be possible for the estimates to indicate different directions of effect and for the test that they are equal to suggest they are.</i>
≥ 0.05	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The magnitude of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST <u>is not sensitive</u> to modelling assumptions. The direction of the effect of being randomized and adhering to NOST <u>is not sensitive</u> to modelling assumptions.

453

454 9.1.2 Sensitivity analysis regarding the unit of primary outcome assessment

455 The unit of randomization and analysis is hospital ward. Hand hygiene compliance is assessed through
 456 structured observation sessions lasting 20-30 minutes. During each session, trained observers follow
 457 one or more healthcare personnel within a single location and document all hand hygiene
 458 opportunities, recording all situations where hand hygiene is or should have been performed. Due to
 459 this session-based observation approach, outcomes may not be statistically independent of one
 460 another and there may be within-session clustering. Sessions are assigned unique codes, making it
 461 possible to identify observations within sessions and hence account for any clustering.

462

463 A sensitivity analysis will be conducted for the primary outcome to explore possible clustering. The
 464 sensitivity analysis will use a hierarchical model with session-code as the unit of analysis, accounting
 465 for potential dependencies of observations within each ward nested in each hospital.

466

467 The estimation can be performed in R as follows:

468

```
469 model <- glmer(cbind(compliance_success, compliance_failure) ~ treat + adh
470                  + (1 | hospital/ward),
471                  data = df,
472                  family = binomial(link = "log"))
473 lincom <- glht(model, linfct = c(treat + adh = 0))
474
```

475

475 If the log-link model fails to converge we will use logistic regression (binomial family with logit link) for
476 the primary and sensitivity analyses to estimate odds ratios.

477

478 ICCs for the level of both hospitals and for the wards within hospitals will be calculated and reported
479 as described in 9.1.

480 9.2 Mean Difference Estimation

481 The previous version of this SAP proposed analyzing length of hospital stay as a continuous variable.
482 As a result of ongoing discussions, it was decided that this outcome should probably be treated as a
483 time-to-event model, and that there are several statistical issues that may need to be treated more
484 carefully (e.g., the possibility that a patient could be moved from an intervention ward to a control
485 ward, or vice versa, and that there could be competing risks, such as death). Consequently, we will
486 write a separate SAP and publish results for this outcome separately.

487 10 7.69.19.19.1.1 Estimands

488 This section presents all estimands in terms of the objective, a statement of the estimand in plain
489 language, the target population (i.e., who or what the estimate can be applied to), the analysis set
490 (i.e., what subset, if any, of the full analysis set will be used to perform the analysis), the outcome
491 variable, strategies for handling ICEs and missing data, the effect measure that will be estimated, and
492 the estimator used to perform the analysis.

493 10.1 Primary Outcome Estimand

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to compliance with hand hygiene recommendations.

Estimand The risk of compliance with hand hygiene recommendations, measured at one year, by employees who perform patient-related work in Norwegian hospitals if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.

Target population Employees

Analysis set All

Outcome Variable Compliance with hand hygiene recommendations

ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1

Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5

Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD

Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-robust standard errors

494

495 10.2 Secondary Outcome Estimands

496 10.2.1 Outbreaks (VESUV)

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to outbreaks.

Estimand The risk of outbreak, measured over one year, in Norwegian hospital wards if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.

Target population Hospital wards	Analysis set All
Outcome Variable Outbreaks (VESUV)	
ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1	Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5
Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD	Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-robust standard errors

497 **10.2.2 Inpatient Infection (VESUV)**

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to inpatient infection (using data from VESUV).	
Estimand The risk of inpatient infection defined as part of an outbreak, measured over one year, in Norwegian hospital wards if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.	
Target population Inpatients	Analysis set Wards with reported outbreak
Outcome Variable Inpatient infections (VESUV)	
ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1	Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5
Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD	Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-robust standard errors

498 **10.2.3 Employee Infection (VESUV)**

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to employee infection.	
Estimand The risk of employee infection as defined part of an outbreak, measured over one year, in Norwegian hospital wards if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.	
Target population Employees	Analysis set Wards with reported outbreak
Outcome Variable Employee infections (VESUV)	
ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1	Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5
Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD	Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-robust standard errors

499 **10.2.4 Inpatient Infection (NOIS)**

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to inpatient infection (using data from NOIS).	
Estimand The risk of inpatient infection, measured over one year in repeated prevalence studies, in Norwegian hospital wards if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.	
Target population Inpatients	Analysis set Wards participating in the surveillance
Outcome Variable Inpatient infection (NOIS)	
ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1	Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5
Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD	Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-robust standard errors

500 **10.2.5 Inpatient Antibiotic Treatment (NOIS)**

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to inpatient antibiotic treatment.	
Estimand The risk of inpatient antibiotic treatment, measured over one year in repeated prevalence studies, in Norwegian hospital wards if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.	
Target population Inpatients	Analysis set Wards participating in the surveillance
Outcome Variable Inpatient antibiotic treatment (NOIS)	
ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1	Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5
Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD	Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-

robust standard errors

501 **10.2.6 Inpatient Postoperative Site Infection (NOIS-POSI)**

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to inpatient treatment for postoperative site infection.

Estimand The risk of postoperative site infection, measured over one year in periods of incidence surveillance of patients undergoing certain surgical procedures, in Norwegian hospital wards if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.

Target population Inpatients undergoing surgical procedures monitored in NOIS-POSI groups (included in the NOIS-POSI surveillance)

Outcome Variable Inpatient postoperative site infection (NOIS-POSI)

ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1

Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5

Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD

Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-robust standard errors

502 **10.2.7 Inpatient HAI Diagnosis (NPR)**

Objective To assess the effect of NOST with respect to inpatient HAI diagnosis.

Estimand The risk of inpatient HAI diagnosis, measured over one year, in Norwegian hospital wards if NOST was introduced and adhered to versus if NOST was not introduced and not adhered to.

Target population Inpatients

Analysis set Hospitalized patients in inpatient wards

Outcome Variable Inpatient HAI diagnosis (NPR)

ICE Strategy See sections 7.6, 9.1, and 9.1.1

Missing Data Strategy See section 7.5

Effect Measure(s) RR and indicative RD

Estimator Binomial regression with cluster-robust standard errors

503 **11 Reporting Conventions**

504 In general, percentages in the table of baseline characteristics will be rounded to whole numbers, and
505 summaries of continuous variables will be presented to one decimal place.

506

507 Statistical estimates will be presented as points with two-sided 95% confidence intervals and *p*-values.

508 Point estimates and confidence intervals will be reported to 2 decimal places, and *p*-values will be

509 reported to three decimal places or as $p < 0.001$.

510 **12 Quality Assurance of Statistical Programming**

511 The statistical code will be written and tested on fictitious data. Testing will include producing all
512 results, tables, and figures as they will appear in the final manuscript prior to analyzing the trial data.

513

514 Analysis code and data will be versioned using an appropriate system to be chosen by the analyst and
515 may be published alongside the trial results.

516 **13 Summary of Changes to the Protocol and/or SAP**

517 This section is to be completed to document and justify any changes to a published version of this SAP.

518 **14 Acknowledgements**

519 The template used to produce this SAP was derived with permission from a template developed by
520 the Michigan Institute for Clinical and Health Research (MICHR; grant UL1TR002240), which was based
521 in turn on version CCTU/TPLV2 of the template produced by Cambridge University Hospitals Clinical
522 Trials Unit.

523 **15 References**

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528